

Title: The Double-Edged Sword of Integrity Assessment in Evidence synthesis

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Dear editor

We read with great interest the individual participant data meta-analysis (IPD-MA) by Zou et al. on intrauterine human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) administration before embryo transfer (Zou *et al.*, 2026). This work represents a commendable and methodologically ambitious contribution to reproductive medicine. The integration of trustworthiness assessment into an IPD-MA framework reflects exactly the kind of rigorous scrutiny that the field of IVF add-ons urgently needs. The authors' efforts to obtain individual participant data from trial investigators, and their transparency in reporting the limitations of the non-IPD evidence base, deserve recognition.

However, the reliability of integrity assessment depends critically on its consistent and transparent application. Upon independent re-evaluation of the seven IPD-included trials using the same tools employed by the authors, we identified at least one major concern in every included IPD trial.

Applying the authors' own rule — that a single domain with major concerns is sufficient to classify a trial as a major concern — all seven trials would fail trustworthiness criteria under consistent application of this standard. We respectfully present these findings and their implications below.

Integrity Re-evaluation

We re-evaluated the integrity of the included studies using the same tools applied in the IPD-MA (Mol *et al.*, 2023; Hunter *et al.*, 2024). We first applied the IPD integrity tool (13 study-level and 18 IPD-specific domains); *however*, due to lack of access to IPD, only study-level items were assessed. To validate our findings, we conducted an additional assessment using the Trustworthiness in RAndomised Clinical Trials (TRACT) checklist.

Re-assessment of the 13 study-level domains of the IPD integrity tool identified at least one major concern in every included study (Table 1). The concerns identified in our assessment were major yet had been rated as “no issues” in the IPD-MA. These included absent, retrospective, or inconsistent trial registration; multiple retractions within author groups; implausible authorship patterns; lack of reported informed consent; implausible follow-up; and implausible results (Table 1). Applying the authors' own rule — that a single domain with major concerns classifies a study as failing

trustworthiness criteria — all seven IPD trials would be excluded under consistent application of this standard.

One Rule, Two Verdicts

The most striking inconsistency concerns the handling of author retractions. The original IPD-MA excluded one trial following integrity assessment because of multiple retractions within the authors' group. Yet one included RCT (Abdallah *et al.*, 2021)— which shares an identical concern, with six retracted publications identified among its authors' group — was rated as "no issues" and included in the primary analysis. Notably, this is not an isolated inconsistency: retrospective registration was classified as a major concern in non-IPD trials yet was rated as “no issues” in other IPD trial (Laokirkkiat *et al.*, 2019). This differential treatment of substantively equivalent integrity signals is unexplained and represents an internal inconsistency within the review's own methodology.

Gatekeeping or Goal-Shifting?

Although integrity assessment tools represent a major step forward in safeguarding evidence synthesis from untrustworthy trials, their application is not without risk (Khan *et al.*, 2023). When applied incautiously, these tools may themselves become a source of bias. Subjective judgments, underweighting of critical concerns, or inconsistent domain ratings can lead to misclassification of studies, potentially allowing flawed evidence to persist while excluding valid data. Moreover, lack of transparency in how decisions are made may obscure potential biases or influence judgments.

Integrity assessment, therefore, should be held to the same standards of rigor, reproducibility, and transparency as other methodological components of evidence synthesis (Li *et al.*, 2020; Khan *et al.*, 2025). Otherwise, the process risks becoming a new source of bias rather than a safeguard against it.

No Trial Left Behind

If all available trials—both IPD and non-IPD—are affected by significant integrity concerns, then the evidence base for intrauterine hCG as an add-on intervention may represent an extreme case in which no study can be confidently considered trustworthy. Similar scenarios have been observed in other

areas of reproductive medicine, where rigorous integrity reassessment has led to the exclusion of entire bodies of evidence (Wang, 2025).

This does not diminish the value of IPD meta-analysis as a methodological approach, nor the importance of integrity assessment tools. Rather, it highlights that the reliability of such approaches depends critically on consistent, transparent, and rigorous application (Khan *et al.*, 2025). Selective or inconsistent interpretation of integrity signals risks introducing a new form of bias—one that may be less visible but equally consequential.

The Path Forward

The recent IPD-MA (Zou *et al.*, 2026) does not report whether thresholds for borderline signals were defined before assessment began. Without a pre-registered protocol, the rating process is vulnerable to post-hoc justification. Future IPD meta-analyses should consider publishing domain-level decision rules alongside their PROSPERO registration, before any trial author is contacted.

Independence in assessment is critical. Assessors who have invested months in building collaborative relationships with trial investigators, negotiating data sharing agreements, and managing complex datasets may not be ideally positioned to then rule those same datasets untrustworthy. The structural proximity between data collection and integrity assessment in the IPD-MA is not a failure of intent — it is a design limitation that the field should address proactively. Independent, blinded duplicate assessment — conducted by reviewers with no involvement in data collection — should be considered, with disagreements resolved by a third party.

Finally, the field should consider moving beyond binary classifications of trustworthiness. Reducing complex integrity profiles to a simple “include” or “exclude” decision risks oversimplification and loss of potentially informative data. A more nuanced approach—such as integrity-weighted models, in which each study’s contribution is scaled according to its integrity profile—may better capture uncertainty while minimizing distortion.

In conclusion, our independent re-evaluation identifies major integrity concerns in every trial included in the IPD-MA. When consistent criteria leave no trial meeting trustworthiness standards on either

side, the only defensible conclusion is insufficient evidence — not evidence of no effect. These are clinically distinct statements with different consequences for patients and practice. Taken together, these observations point toward a more rigorous approach to integrity assessment — one that is systematic, transparent, and resilient to bias. Without such evolution, integrity tools risk becoming not only gatekeepers of evidence, but also inadvertent sources of distortion.

Author contributions

YM: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing– original draft, Writing– review & editing. A.E: Investigation, Writing– original draft. N.AE: Investigation, Writing– original draft. All authors contributed to interpreting the findings, revising and editing the article. All authors approved the final version before submission.

Funding

No funds were received.

Generative AI statement

In preparing this manuscript, the author used artificial intelligence (AI) tools to enhance the clarity of writing and check spelling and grammar. Prior to submission, the author reviewed the content edited by AI and took full responsibility for the content of the submitted manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors report no conflict of interest.

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